

Readiness of HRM Departments in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to Integrate Artificial Intelligence Technologies into Their Practices

Author Details: Hala Ahmed Maalla

Public Administration Department -College of Business Administration- King Saud University
Riyadh - Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

The aim of this study was to measure the readiness of these departments to apply artificial intelligence based on several variables that have been shown through the literature to have their impact on the application of artificial intelligence in human resources departments. In addition, the study aimed to identify the factors directly and indirectly affecting this application; as a first stage, qualitative data (theoretical framework and preliminary interviews) were collected and analyzed; the qualitative results were then used to build quantitative measurement tools for the study, where a targeted questionnaire was designed for managers of human resources departments and tested via a survey study. After confirming their validity, the data was collected and analyzed. The most important findings of the study were that there is an average readiness among government human resources departments in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to apply artificial intelligence, by measuring axes with specific indicators included in a questionnaire distributed to the managers of human resources departments in government agencies such as ministries, bodies, and others. Managers gave a high rating to the readiness of their departments with respect to certain application-level signals, digital leadership, and reliance on analytics, while giving an average rating of both infrastructure and regulations, and a low rating of both employees' digital skills and open organizational culture. By testing the path analysis, the study came up with a mathematical model that illustrates the relationships and mutual effects between variables on the application of artificial intelligence. The results of the analysis concluded that digital leadership, reliance on analytics, and infrastructure were all having a direct impact on the application of artificial intelligence. Employee skills and an open organizational culture have had an indirect impact on the application of AI.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence – Human Resource Management

Introduction:

Advances in artificial intelligence (AI) have attracted increasing interest from researchers and practitioners and have opened many valuable opportunities for the use of AI in the work environment of the government sector. Artificial intelligence has been applied gradually and cautiously in government organizations to help make decisions, helping managers accelerate their routine and repetitive daily work. It provided a broad database and strong analytical support and allowed to get out of mechanical work and engage in more valuable work for coordination, governance, problem solving, cooperation, and enrichment. employee and community experience, updating strategies and innovation work. Against this background, (Eetgerink, 2019) stated that there is an urgent need to form a comprehensive understanding of the scope and impact of AI-based applications in the government sector and the challenges associated with them. According to Harvard Business Review in 2019, "AI applications to the public sector are broad and growing, and we need to conduct exploratory experiments around the world and in various contexts." The application of AI in the field of human resource management is one of the most prominent trends among data development professionals and intelligent systems (Adepu et al., 2020). The adoption of AI in HRM can be called the "New Era of Human Resource Management" because AI is expected to change the way resources are managed (Arslan et al.,2021). Completely human. But (Li and Wu, 2018) argue that the application of artificial intelligence technology in human resource management is still proceeding with careful and deliberate steps, especially with a lot of obstacles compared to the speed of progress towards specialized artificial intelligence systems in healthcare, the automotive industry, social media, advertising, marketing, and others that have been large and enormous. (Agar, 2019) indicates that far less progress has been made on issues related to human resource management; especially in the government sector (KPMG, 2019). This may be due to the complexity of the nature of HR management's work, the challenges of government data in HR management tasks and processes, justice and legal constraints, and employee feedback to AI

management. However, AI provides HR management with valuable insights into career development, human asset management, leadership preparation, workforce planning, and the formulation of a successful strategy to attract and retain talent.

Research Justification:

One of the things that has caught the attention of researchers and theorists in this field about the importance of organizational readiness for the application of artificial intelligence is what has been revealed by studies (Chelliah, 2017, Abdeldayem and Aldulai, 2020; Merlin and Jayam, 2018) is that many government organizations have not made early radical shifts to AI technologies, and therefore it may take years to establish them in the government sector. But once established, it can become a matter of survival for those organizations. Organizations, according to Johansson and Herranen (2019), must understand their needs and evaluate their assets in terms of their application in their work.

There is a lack of research that is supposed to explore how AI affects government human resource departments. Little research has been done in the form of case studies, especially in specific contexts, and research on AI applications used in functional human resource management has focused on improving decision-making and problem-solving skills in activities such as recruitment and selection, video interviews, and exploring the psychological contracts between man and machine at work, Team Composition, Selection and Performance Evaluation, and Talent Management Expectations. Therefore, (Malik et al. 2020) argue it is necessary to highlight areas that require in-depth analysis, conceptual perspectives, and new theoretical frameworks to answer key questions in the application of artificial intelligence in human resource management, especially in the government sector. These studies and research are currently being conducted in several countries, where the labor market, organizational culture, administrative laws, and working conditions differ from the prevailing conditions in Saudi Arabia, and the question here is whether the results of this research are applicable in the Kingdom. Based on this vision, the problem of the study revolves around the following questions: How willing are HR departments in Saudi Arabia to integrate AI technologies into their departments?

Methodology:

This study community includes managers of human resources departments in various government organizations in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and everyone named under the name of this profession according to the Saudi classification of professions. This community was chosen to collect quantitative data on the evaluation of human resources departments in relation to the application of artificial intelligence, given that the nature of evaluation data (related to policies and strategies) is the most relevant to the nature of their work.

Study Tool:

A questionnaire has been prepared to collect the necessary data for this study. This questionnaire consists of the basic dimensions in the evaluation of human resources departments: digital leadership, digital transformation; reliance on analytics and metrics; regulations; open organizational culture; and infrastructure. Each dimension contains indicators in particular, measuring it correctly is related to the study. This questionnaire consists of 41 closed statements that are answered by choosing one answer out of five options according to the five-point Likert scale about the extent to which they agree with the statement (very agree, agree, neutral, disagree, disagree at all). As shown in Table 1, The questionnaire was also judged by two arbitrators, two university professors, one specializing in human resources management and the other specializing in artificial intelligence. It was approved for distribution by the Scientific Research Ethics Committee at King Saud University.

Table No. (1) Elements of the questionnaire to assess the level of readiness of government human resources departments to apply artificial intelligence

M	axles	Indicators
1	Digital Leadership	Knowledge and perception – Analysis of the work environment – Leadership of change
2	Digital Transformation	Digital Strategy – Ensuring Data Flow – Continuous Evaluation
3	Reliance on analytics and metrics	Its existence – its application – the benefit of it
4	Digital Employee Skills	Understanding Engagement – Handling Information – Organizational Support
5	Regulations	Understanding Variables – Data Security and Privacy – Keeping Up with Digital Progress
6	Open Organizational Culture	Philosophy of teamwork – adaptability – ability to be creative
7	Infrastructure	Availability of systems for data processing and storage - Availability of an information security system - Availability of budget in the organization for the development of information technology

Due to the adoption of this questionnaire only to the managers of human resources departments in the government sector in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, whether applied or not applied to artificial intelligence techniques, the methodology of the control sample or the target sample was adopted, which is a non-probabilistic method of sampling where the members of the sample are selected only on the basis of the knowledge and judgment of the researcher, because the knowledge of the researcher plays a fundamental role in the creation of the sample in this method of sampling. Chances are that the results obtained are very accurate with a minimum margin of error. The questionnaire was distributed electronically to the managers of human resources departments, as well as training a number of volunteers in order to deliver the questionnaire on paper to the concerned authorities, whether in their employer or the governorate in which they are located and follow them up through the establishment of a working group to ensure the progress of their work and answer their inquiries. Data was obtained from eighty-two government managers of the Human Resources Department and the like, according to the classification of Saudi professions.

Results:

To classify the readiness of human resources departments in the Saudi public sector to apply artificial intelligence techniques to (high readiness-medium readiness-low readiness), an estimated balance of the length of the period was developed (from 1 to 1.79), based on the five-year Likert scale of the evaluation questionnaire. Accordingly, the answers (absolutely disagree and disagree) are considered to be within the low readiness level, the answers (neutral) are considered to be within the intermediate readiness level, and the answers (agree and strongly agree) are considered to be within the high readiness level. According to the following table,

Table No. (2) Estimated Scale According to the Likert Pentagonal Scale of the assessment Questionnaire

Responsiveness	Weighted average in weights	Length of time	Level
absolutely disagree	1 to 1.79	0.79	low
disagree	From 1.80 to 2.59	0.79	
neutral	From 2.60 to 3.39	0.79	medium
agree	3.40 to 4.19	0.79	High
Strongly agree	From 4.20 to 5.00	0.79	

The table below provides a summary of the value of the arithmetic mean of the arithmetic averages obtained from the variables of assessing the readiness of human resources departments to apply artificial intelligence techniques in them, which amounted to (3.2177). Based on the estimated value assumed in the estimated balance, the average from (2.60 to 3.39) is considered an average predisposition, and these answers the first study question about the level of readiness, and the answer is, "There is an average readiness of human resources departments in the government sector in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to apply artificial intelligence.

Table No. (3) Summary of the arithmetic average of all evaluation axes

axles	Application of artificial intelligence	Digital Leadership	Rely on analytics and metrics	Digital Employee Skills	Regulations	Open Organizational Culture	Infrastructure
arithmetic mean	3.351	3.320	3.336	2.579	3.367	2.348	3.223
Total arithmetic mean	3.2177						
Result	medium						

Path analysis, which relies on correlation analysis and regression analysis, was also used to calculate path coefficients, to study the factors influencing the application of artificial intelligence and to study the direct effects and indirect effects of independent variables on the dependent variable.

Variables for the Path Analysis Test

- Dependent variable: AI application Y
- Independent Variables: Digital Leadership X_6
- Infrastructure X_5
- Reliance on analytics and metrics X_4
- Regulations X_3
- Open Organizational Culture X_2
- Digital Employee Skills X_1

To use apath analysis method, the relationship between variables must be linear.

To test the existence of a linear relationship between variables, the assumptions are formulated as follows:

There is a linear relationship between variables: H1

In formulating the models, the following results were obtained indicating that the model of y linear regression between the dependent variable and the independent variables is significant:

Sig	F	R square	
0.000	28.276	0.693	Model

We find that Sig (0.000) is below the level of morale (0.05). This means that the decision and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis H1 which states that there is a linear relationship between variables.

Thus, models can be estimated as follows:

First model (variable of Digital Leadership)

$$X_6 = .158X_1 - .072031 + .738X_2 - .X_3 + .242X_4 X_5$$

Sig	F	R square	
0.000	23.89	0.611	Model

Second model (Variable of Infrastructure)

$$X_5 = .596 - .065X_1 + .1306 + .461X_2 + .X_3 + .017X_4 01X_6$$

Sig	F	R square	
0.000	31.67	0.676	Model

Third model (variable of the Reliance on analytics and metrics)

$$X_4 = .637 + .092X_1 - .064419X_2 - .X_3 + .041X_5 + .323X_6$$

Sig	F	R square	
0.000	13.456	0.47	Model

Fourth model (Variable of Application of Artificial Intelligence)

$$Y = .230 + .015X_1 - .048 + .264 + 435X_2 + .001X_3 + .269X_4 X_5X_6$$

Sig	F	R square	
0.000	28.276	0.693	Model

It is observed in all models Sig (0.000) is below the level of morale (0.05) and therefore all models is statistically significant.

After checking the conditions of the method of testing the analysis of the path in growth yc and after studying the relationship between the variables, the models be as follows:

- (X1) Digital Employee Skills (X2) Open Organizational Culture (X3) Regulations
- (X4) Relying on analytics and metrics (X5) Infrastructure (X6) Digital Driving
- (Y) Application of Artificial Intelligence

The simple correlation coefficients between independent variables were expressed in two-way curve arrows. A stock with a one-way E between external and internal variables expresses the coefficient of path. The value of the path coefficient represents the direct.

Direct effects of independent variables on the dependent variable

It is noted that digital driving has had a direct impact on the application of artificial intelligence with a path coefficient of 0.435. The higher the percentage of digital driving by one unit, the greater the percentage of application of artificial intelligence by 0.435, and the infrastructure directly affects the application of artificial intelligence by a factor Track 0.264, as well as reliance on analytics and metrics directly affect digital transformation with a path coefficient of 0.269.

Based on the above, variables can be arranged according to their direct impact on the application of artificial intelligence as follows in the following table:

Variable	Path coefficient (direct effect)
Digital Driving X6	0.435
Rely on analytics and metrics X5	0.269
Infrastructure X4	0.264

Calculate the indirect effects of variables on the dependent variable (AI application)

The indirect effect of external variables in the internal variable is calculated and expressed in kinetic paths and the value of the compound path is the product of multiplying all the coefficients of the direct paths that make up the compound path.

	Through X4	Through X5	Through X6
Effect X1 in Y	$0.092 * 0.269 = 0.0248$	$0.065 * 0.264 = 0.0172$	$0.158 * 0.435 = 0.0688$
Effect X2 in Y	$-0.064 * 0.269 = -0.0172$	$0.161 * 0.264 = 0.0425$	$-0.072 * 0.435 = -0.0313$
Effect X3 in Y	$0.419 * 0.269 = 0.1127$	$0.306 * 0.264 = 0.0808$	$-0.031 * 0.435 = -0.0135$

Table Abelow shows the direct and indirect effect of independent variables on the dependent variable applying artificial intelligence (Y)

Variable	Direct impact	Indirect impact
Digital Employee Skills X1	0.05	0.0688
Open Organizational Culture X2	-0.048	0.0425
Regulations X3	0.001	0.0808

The table shows that the indirect impact of variables X1, X2, and X3 on the dependent variable is higher than the direct impact, which means that there are variables that indirectly affect the application of artificial intelligence: digital employee skills, open organizational culture, and regulations.

Based on the above, variables can be arranged according to their indirect impact on digital transformation, illustrated as follows in the following table:

	Path coefficient (indirect impact coefficient)
Regulations X3	0.0808
Digital Employee Skills X1	0.0688
Open Organizational Culture X2	0.0425

Theoretical and applied contributions to this study:

This study is particularly important given the need for new and interdisciplinary theoretical contributions and assumptions on the topics of artificial intelligence and human resource management. The contributions of this study can be seen in theoretical and practical terms as follows:

Researchers agree that there is a vacuum in the overlap between areas of research in organizational and technological research. We hope that this study will contribute to filling this void with statistically proven results and hypotheses that help to understand the real relationship between public administration, human

resource management, and artificial intelligence technology. This study opens the door to further research from several perspectives that will broaden our understanding of the impact of artificial intelligence on government organizations and human assets operating in the public service.

The Applied Contribution: The debate on AI and its implications for work and human resource management is still new and controversial in nature among many researchers and theorists, who have argued that to move forward, leaders, especially in government organizations, have to deal with the challenges of cultural, humanitarian, and social mindsets to implement AI applications in the workplace and to form a deep understanding of the role of humans in dealing with AI, which is more important now than ever. The tools of this study provide an important measure for managers to evaluate their departments in terms of readiness as a first stage, from the point of view of integrating applications as a second stage and evaluating the success of the application later.

References

- Abdeldayem M and Aldulaimi S, (2020), *Trends and Opportunities of Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management: Aspirations for Public Sector In Bahrain*, *International journal of scientific and technology research*, volume 9, issue 1, pp 3867-3871.
- Adepu, K, Agarwal, K, Chitranshi, J, Nagendra, A, Islam, T, (2020), *Study of usage of artificial intelligence in human resource in it industry*. *Indian J. Ecol.* Issue 47, pp132–134.
- Agar, N. (2019). *How to be Human in the Digital Economy*, MIT Press.
- Arslan, A., Cooper, C. , Khan, Z. , Golgeci, I. and Ali, I. (2021), "Artificial intelligence and human workers interaction at team level: a conceptual assessment of the challenges and potential HRM strategies", *International Journal of Manpower*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-01-2021-0052>.
- Chelliah J, (2017) "Will artificial intelligence usurp white collar jobs?", *Human Resource Management International Digest*, Vol. 25 Issue: 3, pp.1-3, doi: 10.1108/HRMID-11-2016-0152.
- Eetgerink K, (2019), *Government are coming for artificial intelligence, a comparative case study of France and the United Kingdom*, Master thesis, MA European Union Studies, Leiden University, Netherland.
- Johansson, J, Herranen, S, (2019), *the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Human Resource Management: Current state of AI and its impact on the traditional recruitment process*, diva-portal.org.
- KPMG, (2019), *the future of HR –Saudi Arabia HR survey*. KPMG network.
- Li, Y. L., Wu, X. H. (2018), *A Brief Analysis of the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Human Resource Management*. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, issue (03): pp 400-401.
- Malik, A., Srikanth, N.R., & Budhwar, P, (2020), *Digitization, AI and HRM*. In J. Crashaw & P. Budhwar (Eds.) *Strategic Human Resource Management*. UK: Sage Publications.
- Merlin.P, Jayam.R, (2018), *Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management*, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, Volume 119 No. 17, pp1891-1895.